

Hydrothermal calderas

by

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Abstract

The standard model of caldera formation is related to the emptying of a magma chamber and ensuing roof collapse during large eruptions or subsurface withdrawal. Although this model works well for numerous volcanoes, it is inappropriate for many basaltic volcanoes (with the notable exception of Hawaii), as these have eruptions that involve volumes of magma that are small compared to the collapse. Many arc volcanoes also have similar oversized depressions, such as Poas (Costa Rica) and Aoba (Vanuatu).

In this article, we propose an alternative caldera model based on deep hydrothermal alteration of volcanic rocks in the central part of the edifice. Under certain conditions, the clay-rich altered and pressurised core may flow under its own weight, spread laterally, and trigger very large caldera-like collapse. Several specific mechanisms can generate the formation of such hydrothermal calderas. Among them, we identify two principal modes: Mode I: Ripening with summit loading and flank spreading; and Mode II: Unbuttressing with flank subsidence and flank sliding. Processes such as summit loading or flank subsidence may act simultaneously in hybrid mechanisms. Natural examples are shown to illustrate the different modes of formation. For Ripening, we give Aoba (Vanuatu) as an example of probable summit loading, while Casita (Nicaragua) is the type example of flank spreading. For Unbuttressing, Nuku Hiva Island (Marquesas) is our example for flank subsidence, and Piton de la Fournaise (La Réunion) is our example of flank sliding.

The whole process is slow, and needs probably a) at least a few tens of thousand years to deeply alter the edifice and reach conditions suitable for ductile flow and b) a few hundred years to achieve the caldera collapse. The size and the shape of the caldera strictly mimic that of the underlying weak core. Thus, the size of the caldera is not controlled by the dimensions of the underlying magma reservoir. A collapsing hydrothermal caldera could generate significant phreatic activity and trigger major eruptions from a co-existing magmatic complex. As the buildup to collapse is slow, such caldera forming events could be detected long before their onset.

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1 **Introduction**

2

3 Calderas are one of the most spectacular geological structures encountered on Earth.
4 Derived from the Portuguese word “caldeira” meaning cauldron, a caldera is a large circular
5 flat-lying floor depression, bounded by vertical cliffs, that can truncate horizontally the upper
6 part of a volcano. The size of a caldera ranges from the kilometre scale (e.g. 2.5-km-wide for
7 the Pinatubo caldera, Philippines) to as much as 80 km in width (e.g. 30 × 80 km-wide for the
8 Toba caldera on Sumatra Island) (Lipman 2000a). The steep walls surrounding the caldera
9 may be up to hundreds of meters high.

10 In the standard magmatic model, calderas form following a large volcanic eruption,
11 that empties the edifice magma reservoir. The principal mechanism (i.e. the piston model) is
12 that of a coherent upper block, plate-like geometry and more or less cylindrical, that subsides
13 along well-defined ring faults into the emptying reservoir (e.g. Lipman 1984, 1997, 2000b).
14 Numerous field and experimental studies have shown the relevance of the model (e.g., Smith
15 and Bailey 1968; Oftedhal 1978; Druitt and Sparks 1984; Komuro 1987; Marti et al. 1994;
16 Roche et al. 2000; Acocella et al. 2000; Troll et al. 2002). Although other mechanisms may
17 also be important (i.e. trap-door, non coherent collapse, downsag or funnel models, e.g.
18 Branney and Kokelaar 1994; Walker 1984; Yokoyama 1981; Troll et al. 2002), they all
19 invoke the presence of an underlying magma chamber which, when evacuated by large
20 eruptions, leads to the collapse of its roof into a depressurised volume.

21 This standard model implies a strong correlation between the size of the caldera and
22 that of the underlying reservoir. To form a gigantic caldera of several tens of kilometres wide
23 requires a magma chamber of an equivalent size. For example, the total erupted volume of the
24 of the 75 ka old Toba eruption is about 1500 km³, which corresponds to one of the largest

25 eruptions ever recorded on Earth (Lipman, 2000a). The area of Toba caldera is roughly 1500
26 km², requiring a melt layer at least 1 km thick in the crust to have been evacuated.

27 Explosive eruptions are commonly associated with the formation of huge calderas,
28 involving large volumes of ignimbrites for both silicic and basaltic volcanoes (Druitt and
29 Sparks 1984; Lipman 2000a; Walker 1988). However, some volcanoes, in particular basaltic
30 shields, reveal a specific problem that has rarely been taken into account, and which justifies
31 the search of an alternative model. For these volcanoes, such as Piton de la Fournaise Volcano
32 on Reunion Island (Indian Ocean) or Nuku Hiva Volcano (Marquesas, French Polynesia), the
33 caldera depression is much larger than the volume of erupted products, and geological and
34 geophysical evidence indicates that no large magma chamber has existed.

35 One explanation is that repeated or step-by-step collapse has occurred, as has been
36 proposed for Kilauea (e.g. Holcomb et al. 1988). This model is supported by voluminous lava
37 flows discovered on the surrounding seafloor off Hawaii. An alternative possibility has been
38 proposed by Walker (1988) where the caldera results from the sinking of dense intrusive
39 complexes in the lithosphere. Such a model has been applied to the Galapagos (Munro and
40 Rowland 1996).

41 In this paper, we propose a different model of caldera formation based on the
42 deformation and flow of volcanic rocks altered by hydrothermal circulation in a volcano core.
43 We propose this alternative model for where a small magma chamber is associated with a
44 large overlying caldera. This new type of caldera, termed *hydrothermal caldera* as opposed to
45 *magmatic caldera*, may occur without a major eruption. Alternatively, the generation of a
46 hydrothermal caldera could trigger phreatic eruptions and cause the disruption of an
47 accompanying magma chamber, leading to classic caldera collapse.

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50 **Caldera and hydrothermal alteration**

51

52 A hydrothermal system consists of hot fluids that reside or flux through an area of
53 rock that becomes highly altered as a result. Hydrothermal alteration can be widespread in a
54 volcanic setting, because a volcano provides both a heat source and a source of fluids. The
55 heat source comes from the magma itself, either propagating upward, laterally and diagonally
56 through dykes, or stored into one or several reservoirs. Hot fluids come from meteoric waters
57 heated when approaching the magmatic heat source and from magmatic gases released from
58 the magma. Water vapour (H₂O) and carbon dioxide (CO₂) are the principal components of
59 magmatic gas, also comprising other components such as SO₂ and H₂S. The hot mixture of
60 meteoric water and magmatic gases, involving mineralogical, chemical and textural changes
61 of the country rock, causes extensive dissolution and formation of a wide variety of new
62 minerals such as gypsum and clay minerals (e.g. Kerr 1955; Gillott 1987; Hoschtein and
63 Browne 2000). The hydrothermal fluids also have high pressures, and pore fluid pressure
64 tends to reduce the effective strength of the rock mass, and under certain circumstances can
65 fluidize the mass, creating hydrothermal breccias.

66 The degree of alteration is mostly a function of fluid temperature, lithostatic pressure,
67 duration of hydrothermal activity, chemical composition of hydrothermal fluids, host rock
68 composition and permeability (e.g. Walker 1960 a and b). The amount of meteoric water
69 plays an important role in the process, and wetter climates promote extensive alteration.

70 When alteration is pervasive due to an active hydrothermal system and the high
71 permeability of rocks, the mechanical behaviour of the altered zone may change drastically.
72 Changing a brecciated and volcanoclastic zone of ash deposits or lava flow units to a zone of
73 sulphate and clay minerals promotes ductile deformation instead of brittle. At a macroscopic
74 scale, clay and gypsum deform continuously under the action of a shear stress, no matter how

75 small the stress, and can be considered to act as viscous fluids (Middleton and Wilcock 1996).
76 Salt tectonics is a classic example of this process (e.g. Jackson et al. 1994). This means that a
77 deeply altered volcanic core may flow under its own weight; this is the key point of the
78 formation of hydrothermal calderas.

79 Several authors have shown the importance of hydrothermal alteration for volcano
80 collapse (Siebert 1984; Lopez and Williams 1993; Carasco-Nunez et al. 1993 ; Frank 1995;
81 Day 1996; Voight and Elsworth 1997; Iverson et al., 1997; van Wyk de Vries et al. 2000;
82 Reid et al. 2001); such a mechanism is now widely acknowledged by the scientific
83 community. So far, researchers have mainly focussed their interest on hydrothermally altered
84 flanks. Central areas of edifices, which are closer to the heat source (i.e. the magma chamber)
85 and represent potentially more altered zones.

86 However, as shown by analogue modelling (van Wyk de Vries et al. 2000; Merle and
87 Lénat 2003; Cecchi et al. 2005, Merle et al. 2006; Barde-Cabusson and Merle 2007; Barde-
88 Cabusson 2007) a deeply altered core is able to flow under its own weight and may not
89 remain stable. Due to boundary change conditions or merely the overburden gradient, the
90 pseudo-viscous hydrothermally altered core may slowly deform, collapse and/or spread. The
91 way it deforms may lead to vertical re-adjustment of its overlying brittle roof.

92 Hydrothermal systems strictly confined within calderas are not uncommon in
93 volcanoes. From geophysical data, this pattern has been observed for Stromboli (Italy)
94 (Finizola et al. 2002, 2006), Misti (Peru) (Finizola et al. 2004; Tort and Finizola 2005),
95 Karthala (Comoros) (Lénat et al., 1998) and Piton de la Fournaise (Reunion Island) (Lénat et
96 al. 2000) volcanoes. It may be asked whether, subsequent to the collapse, the ring faults serve
97 as structural barriers and contain the alteration within the caldera or, by contrast, if the
98 alteration prior to vertical collapse determines the subsequent location of the ring fault. In this
99 respect, SP measurements that were made before vertical collapse at Stromboli on the 5 April

100 2003 revealed that the collapse occurred along the limit of the SP positive anomalies inferred
101 to represent the main limit of hydrothermal circulation (Finizola et al. 2003; Calvari et al.
102 2006). This is consistent with the hypothesis that, prior to vertical collapse, the extent of the
103 hydrothermal system served as a guide for ring fault formation.

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105

106 **The example of Reunion Island**

107

108 To tackle the problem of hydrothermal calderas, we examine the case of Piton de la
109 Fournaise volcano on Reunion Island (Indian Ocean). Reunion is about 5 Ma old, exhibiting a
110 complex history with rapid destructive mass-wasting events followed by long construction
111 periods, together with the migration of the eruptive centre. The present-day active volcano is
112 less than 600 ka in age and displays four large nested calderas (Bachèlery 1981; Bachèlery
113 and Mairine 1990). The smallest and most recent caldera, the Enclos Fouqué Caldera, is about
114 9 km wide whereas the largest is about 12 km in width. In the centre of the Enclos Fouqué,
115 the active cone rises 400 m from the caldera floor. On top of this cone, the Dolomieu crater is
116 a 1×0.75 km wide structure which has suffered multiple stages of lava infill and collapse.

117 Geophysical surveys indicate that the present-day magma chamber is of small
118 dimension and located 1-2 kilometres below Dolomieu crater. Geophysical data do not show
119 any evidence of a large, dense underlying reservoir; there is no seismic hypocenter
120 distribution compatible with a broad source below the Enclos, nor is there a pronounced
121 positive gravity anomaly below Piton de la Fournaise (Rousset et al. 1989; Neceressian et al.
122 1996; Briole et al. 1998; Malengreau et al. 1999). In addition, many olivine – rich xenoliths
123 are erupted on Piton de la Fournaise, and the oceanite lavas such as those erupted in 2007 are

124 clearly cumulates. Thus, a large magma chamber would have most probably left a cumulate
125 residue that would provide high velocities and a positive gravity anomaly.

126 The lack of gravity and seismic anomaly is in contrast to Piton des Neiges, where a
127 large gravity high, high seismic velocities and drill cores show the presence of a major
128 intrusive body. This body is also associated with voluminous acid ignimbrite eruptions and
129 the probable formation of a magmatic caldera. While a large magma chamber could have
130 formed and emptied completely at Piton de la Fournaise, the necessary large-volume
131 equivalent lava flows have not been observed on land or offshore. This contrasts to Hawaii,
132 which is often regarded as an analogue to Piton de La Fournaise. In many basaltic systems,
133 subsurface drainage of magma from a reservoir occurs and may explain why the caldera
134 volume is so much larger than the volume of erupted products. At Piton de la Fournaise,
135 subsurface drainage also occurs, as testified by numerous linear fissures and/or pre-eruptive
136 dyke-associated uplift in the vicinity of the central cone. However, these kinds of magmatic
137 manifestations are most often located within the large Enclos Fouqué caldera, not outside,
138 suggesting that these subsurface drainages may not be related to caldera subsidence.
139 Moreover, when considering historic eruptions, both subsurface drainage and lava flows can
140 be related to multiple collapse events of the Dolomieu crater, which seems to behave as a
141 standard magmatic caldera associated with a small magma reservoir underneath.

142 In April 2007, Piton de La Fournaise experienced the most voluminous eruption
143 observed in historic times, during which a total volume of about 0.12 km³ of lava was
144 emitted. These lavas first swamped the Dolomieu crater overflowing its rim. Then the main
145 volume of lavas flowed down to the sea from a vent that opened laterally at low elevation on
146 the volcano flank. Towards the end of this impressive eruption, the Dolomieu crater collapsed
147 over several hours, following the trace of the pre-existing crater rim, and produced a 350 m
148 deep new crater, with a collapse volume of about 0.1-0.15 km³ (Bachèlery 2007).

149 This major episode in the recent history of Dolomieu crater reveals that lavas from the
150 shallow reservoir are regularly evacuated, triggering the formation of a standard caldera on
151 top of the central active cone. However, the lack of magma accumulation in a very large
152 reservoir suggests that the standard model of caldera formation for the Enclos Fouqué is
153 problematic. For the same reason, the standard model is also improbable for the larger
154 calderas surrounding the Enclos Fouqué.

155 High-amplitude positive anomalies of self-potential (SP) have been attributed to an
156 active hydrothermal system located below the Dolomieu crater (Malengreau et al. 1994;
157 Michel and Zlotnicki 1998). On a larger scale, a geoelectrical study has imaged a zone of very
158 low resistivity that rises to within a few hundred meters of the surface beneath the active
159 summit area and deepens laterally to 1 km at the edge of the Enclos Fouqué caldera (Lénat et
160 al. 2000). In cross section, the low-resistivity zone has the form of a bulge or a low-angle
161 cone centred below the Dolomieu crater and located within the Enclos Fouqué caldera. This
162 zone has been interpreted as the hydrothermal system of the active volcano where rocks are
163 altered, lowering their resistivity (Fig. 1) (Lénat et al. 2000). Beyond the Enclos Fouqué, the
164 resistivity pattern is substantially different so that the hydrothermal system appears to be
165 confined within the caldera.

166 The initiation of the Enclos caldera, 4700 years ago, was associated with a major
167 explosive phreatic event. The tephra deposits overlie an area of about 500 km² with an
168 estimated total volume of about 1 km³ (Mohamed-Abchir et al. 1998). The deposit is
169 dominated by abundant hydrothermally-altered fragments (Bachèlery 1981; Mohamed-Abchir
170 et al. 1998).

171 To sum up the data for Piton de La Fournaise, the Enclos Fouqué caldera shows three
172 remarkable features: a) there is no evidence of a magma chamber large enough to account for
173 the formation of a large caldera, b) a large zone of deeply altered rocks has developed at the

174 scale of the caldera and c) a phreatic blast involving deeply-altered materials occurred at the
175 onset of the caldera formation. Taken together, these features indicate that the mechanism
176 leading to the formation of the Enclos Fouqué caldera is probably related to the presence of a
177 very large hydrothermal system, not to the small magma chamber located below the
178 Dolomieu crater.

179

180 **Conceptual model**

181

182 The basic principle of caldera formation, whatever the model, is to decrease the edifice
183 core pressure, allowing a crestal block to subside vertically. In the case of a magmatic caldera,
184 the eruption withdraws the magma and lowers magma chamber pressure. In the case of a
185 hydrothermal caldera, it is the weak core that must flow and lower pressure in order to trigger
186 the vertical roof collapse. It follows that a magmatic caldera may result either from the sudden
187 and catastrophic collapse of the upper block after efficient magma withdrawal or from
188 incremental collapse due to small but recurrent eruptions (e.g. Lipman 1997; Munro and
189 Rowland 1996). In contrast, for hydrothermal calderas, the mechanical behaviour of the weak
190 core does not allow rapid withdrawal, so that the formation of the caldera should be
191 considered a slow process dependent on the rate of ductile flow of hydrothermally altered
192 rocks constituting the altered core.

193 It is important to know the conditions required for triggering the ductile deformation
194 of the weak core and the nature of the deformation process. Importantly, for a ductile buried
195 core able to flow under its own weight, two conditions need to be fulfilled. Firstly the ductile
196 core should not be located below a horizontal overburden, meaning that a surface slope is
197 required. Secondly, lateral resistance should not be too strong as to prevent the ductile core
198 from spreading in the horizontal direction (Barde-Cabusson and Merle 2007). Once these

199 conditions are fulfilled, the ductile core flows and deforms, triggering the instability of the
200 overlying roof.

201 Recent field studies together with analogue experiments have shown that hydrothermal
202 calderas may occur in various environments and that the initiating factors may be quite
203 different (Merle and Lnat 2003; Cecchi et al. 2005; Merle et al. 2006; Barde-Cabusson 2007;
204 Michon et al. in press). In the following sections, we present a synthesis and reappraisal of
205 experimental results, most of them being already published in the literature or in PhD theses
206 (Merle and Lnat 2003 ; Cecchi 2003; Cecchi et al. 2005; Merle et al. 2006; Barde-Cabusson
207 and Merle 2007; Barde-Cabusson 2007), showing that hydrothermal calderas may occur in
208 various environments and that the initiating factors may be quite different. The scaling
209 procedure for experiments and a brief description of analogue materials may be seen in the
210 appendix.

211 From these experiments, we may define two principal modes of hydrothermal caldera
212 formation (Fig. 2). The first mode (Mode I : Ripening) is related to the gradual enhancement
213 of hydrothermal alteration without any modification of the stress pattern within the volcanic
214 edifice from an external cause, except the load increase due to the building of the cone itself.
215 This is mainly a change of mechanical behaviour in the core of the edifice which is
216 responsible for caldera initiation. The initiation of deformation may be due to two separate
217 causes: summit loading (Barde-Cabusson and Merle 2007) and flank spreading (Cecchi et al.
218 2005). The second mode (Mode II : Unbuttressing) is related to an important modification of
219 the stress pattern on the side of the volcano. This may result from flank subsidence or flank
220 sliding. In the following sections, we review these modes of caldera formation to present their
221 evolution and structural features as observed in previous experiments and field studies.

222

223

224 **Mode I : Ripening (Fig. 3a)**

225

226 Youthful volcanoes should not undergo hydrothermal caldera formation as time is
227 needed to slowly and deeply alter the core of the edifice by hydrothermal circulation. It may
228 take a few hundred thousand years to completely transform fresh volcanic rocks into clay-rich
229 rocks before the core of the volcano is sufficiently ripe to start the process under
230 consideration. When this is accomplished, the driving factor of the deformation may be either
231 summit loading or flank spreading.

232

233 *Summit loading*

234 The free surface of a volcano is roughly conical. Slopes may vary according to the
235 type of the edifice and are generally in the range from 30° to 10°. Because of the shape, a
236 horizontal overburden gradient above the altered core is created, with high loading at the
237 centre of the volcano, and low loading along the edge. In an ideal case, this overburden
238 gradient is radially distributed from the centre of the volcano.

239 If the internal part of the edifice is deeply altered by hydrothermal circulation so that
240 its general mechanical behaviour is dominated by gypsum and clay minerals, the overburden
241 gradient promotes downward motion of the top of the central part of the altered core, which is
242 counterbalanced by upward, almost vertical injections along the low overloaded edges,
243 making the shape of the ductile body resemble that of a bowl (Fig. 2 in Barde-Cabusson and
244 Merle 2007).

245 The shape change of the ductile body is associated with three successive stages of
246 deformation in the overlying roof (Fig. 4):

247 1. From the beginning, the summit of the cone becomes first blunted, then slowly flattens to
248 eventually form a large flat-lying upper area. This process occurs without any clear faulting,

249 but significant pervasive deformation probably occurs that would be seen as extensive rock
250 brecciation in nature.

251 2. The second stage corresponds to the progressive appearance of a ring fault surrounding the
252 upper flat-lying area.

253 3. Lastly, the upper flat zone collapses as a whole, like a piston, along the ring fault forming a
254 caldera structure.

255 It makes sense to link a) the shape change of the ductile body to the formation of the
256 upper flat area, b) the formation of the ring fault to the upward migration of the ductile body
257 along the edge of the ductile body and c) the final subsidence to the continuation of these two
258 processes (Fig. 4).

259 This general process is dependant on the initial slope of the cone. With a slope less
260 than 15° , the deformation does not go to completion. An upper flat zone forms on top of the
261 cone, but neither a ring fault nor subsidence of the upper flat zone are observed. This clearly
262 demonstrates that the driving factor of caldera formation is the overburden gradient. Even
263 pervasive and deep alteration by hydrothermal circulation of a large part of the edifice may
264 not be sufficient to initiate deformation. From this result, one can deduce that this mode of
265 hydrothermal caldera formation is more likely for steep volcanoes than for shields.

266 On the flanks of the volcano outside the summit deforming zone, the deformation is
267 small, nearly undetectable, and slopes remain generally constant. However, a slight but
268 significant steepening of these external slopes may be observed at the vicinity of the ring
269 fault. Such a steepening mainly occurs during the first stage of caldera formation (i.e., during
270 the formation of the upper flat-lying area). The example of Aoba, discussed below, resembles
271 this situation.

272 Experiments also reveal that the ductile body must be located high in the edifice to
273 form a true cauldron-shaped caldera (i.e. with a flat-lying floor surrounded by a ring fault),

274 probably to within a few hundred meters below the summit (Cecchi 2003; Cecchi et al. 2005;
275 Barde-Cabusson 2007), such as for Piton de la Fournaise. In addition, when the ductile body
276 is high in the edifice but not sufficiently thick to allow the caldera process to go to
277 completion, the summit flattens as a result of the overburden gradient on the ductile body, and
278 the deformation stops (van Wyk de Vries et al. 2000). If the altered zone is situated deeper in
279 the edifice, sagging of the summit area along a less well-defined ring fault (or ring fault zone)
280 is observed but does not form a flat-lying area, and the initial conical shape of the summit is
281 preserved (Fig. 5 in Cecchi et al. 2005). In this case, summit loading is not the driving force
282 of the process, which is then controlled by flank spreading.

283

284 *Flank spreading* (Fig. 3b)

285 Flank spreading is a slow but important process in volcanic evolution (van Wyk de
286 Vries et al. 2000; Cecchi et al. 2005). It is different from volcano spreading where the whole
287 edifice spreads as a result of the deformation of an underlying weak layer (e.g. Borgia 1994;
288 Merle and Borgia 1996). Flank spreading may occur when hydrothermal alteration enlarges
289 the ductile core to within a few hundred meters of the flank surface. Near the surface, the
290 ductile core overcomes the weak lateral buttress, spreads horizontally and produces slow
291 deformation of the flank, which resembles a concave-convex-concave shape (van Wyk de
292 Vries et al. 2000; Cecchi et al. 2005).

293 The upper concavity results from the summit sagging while the intermediate convexity
294 is a bulge due to lateral spreading of the ductile core. In detail, the bulge is associated with
295 intense fracturing of the flank and is limited downward by a basal thrust that may reach the
296 free surface. After deformation, the ductile core exhibits the form of a soup plate (Fig. 5). The
297 sides of the ductile core, as opposed to those observed in cone loading experiments, which
298 exhibit near-vertical movement, are more oblique, sometimes nearly horizontal, especially

299 towards the end of the experiments. This is due to the weak flank which is too thin to contain
300 the ductile core force, thereby deforming into a bulge.

301 That the deformation may go to completion depends on several factors including the
302 shape ratio of the ductile body, its position within the edifice, and the volumetric fraction of
303 the ductile body versus the whole edifice. The ductile body must be large enough (i.e. close
304 enough to the lateral free surface) comprising at least 10% of the total volume of the edifice
305 for spreading to start (Cecchi et al., 2005).

306 Calderas formed according to this process exhibit a conical summit in the centre,
307 which is sagged and is surrounded by a circular flat-lying zone. The collapse of the flat area
308 along the ring fault is sometimes incipient, and no large cliffs are visible (Fig. 8 in Cecchi et
309 al. 2005). To form a true cauldron-shaped caldera (i.e., one with a flat-lying floor limited by
310 vertical cliffs) requires that the altered body be close enough to the summit so that summit
311 loading takes place simultaneously. This shows that flow of a deeply altered core may be
312 responsible for a large range of caldera-like structures, some of which exhibit a relict of the
313 summit in the centre of the flat area and a small amount of subsidence.

314 In some cases, deformation of the ductile body is asymmetric, and the bulge is not
315 concentrically and equally distributed all around the edifice, but is instead more pronounced
316 in one sector. Here the slope becomes progressively steeper to the point at which landslides
317 are initiated, truncating the bulge. The hydrothermal system may then become unbuttressed
318 making flow of the ductile core easier in this direction. This generally triggers new landslides
319 along the flank, which may be large enough to decapitate the summit of the cone, leaving a
320 horseshoe-shaped scar.

321

322

323 **Mode II : Unbuttressing**

324

325 As stated above, the ductile altered core remains stable when there is limited loading
326 from the overlying cone and when buttressing prevents horizontal spreading. If for some
327 reason, the flank is removed in one sector, the confinement of the ductile altered core is
328 breached, and conditions suitable for lateral spreading may be reached. The ensuing collapse
329 of the central part of the edifice accompanying the outward moving ductile core may then
330 create a hydrothermal caldera, which is generally breached along the unconfined boundary
331 (Fig. 6). Two different mechanisms have been proposed to allow lateral unbuttressing of the
332 volcanic edifice: flank subsidence and flank sliding. Erosion also may be an efficient
333 mechanism to slowly unbuttress a sector of a volcano.

334 We use the term flank sliding to describe the rapid or slow landsliding of a flank of a
335 volcano. This term is equivalent to flank collapse, sector collapse, or debris avalanche used
336 elsewhere, but we believe this term more closely describes the phenomena, discriminates
337 between vertical collapse events (such as calderas), and is similar to the term rockslide used
338 by Glicken et al. (1981) to describe the 'rockslide - debris avalanche' of Mount St. Helens.
339 With this usage there is clear linkage and progression between flank sliding, rockslide - debris
340 avalanche and debris avalanche. The term sliding is also closer to that used in tectonics, e.g.
341 for nappes.

342

343 *Flank subsidence* (Fig. 3c)

344 Regional tectonics exerts a strong control on the structural and magmatic evolution of
345 a volcanic edifice. Lowering part of a volcano may create a lateral boundary along which
346 lateral stresses are reduced dramatically. Two different mechanisms can be identified for flank
347 subsidence. The formation or the re-activation of a regional normal fault passing below a
348 volcano is a simple example. An alternative is the sinking of an ancient dense intrusive

349 complex located below the flank of the volcano, as recently proposed for Piton de la
350 Fournaise (Michon and Saint Ange 2008).

351 Considering the case of a regional normal fault lowering the flank of a volcano along
352 the footwall , part of the hydrothermally altered weak core may be lowered with the subsiding
353 flank. Experiments show that the flow of the ductile core may then occur in this direction
354 (Fig. 3c and 7). Under certain conditions, a hydrothermal caldera may form on the hanging
355 wall. The caldera is breached along the normal fault and overhangs the footwall as for Nuku
356 Hiva volcano in the French Polynesia (Merle et al. 2006).

357 With flank subsidence, the two main conditions required for the caldera formation are
358 either a very slow displacement rate or a limited offset of the regional fault (Merle et al.
359 2006). A high velocity leaves a completely free boundary, which promotes the formation of
360 secondary faults parallel to the main normal fault. Faults develop successively backward
361 away from the free surface. A ring fracture forms late in the hanging wall, but vertical
362 collapse remains very limited. This indicates that the instantaneous formation of a free
363 boundary does not leave sufficient time for the ductile core to achieve slow horizontal
364 spreading distributed within the entire ring fracture.

365 When flank subsidence is slow, caldera formation exhibits the same three successive
366 stages as described above. First, the summit of the cone flattens at the onset of the
367 deformation to form a large upper flat area. Second, slow lateral spreading of the ductile core
368 initiates a ring fault. Third, collapse occurs along the ring fault forming a caldera that is
369 breached on one side. During the process, the weak core slowly flows from the hanging wall
370 to the footwall resulting in the formation of a small ridge located on the footwall. The ridge is
371 limited along its base by a thrust fault similar to the bulge formed during flank spreading (Fig.
372 3c and 7).

373 The footwall may also be located beyond the edge of the weak core, which may
374 remain undisturbed on the hanging wall. In this case, the deformation mimics that of flank
375 spreading, the edge of the weak core being next to the lateral free surface of the volcano as a
376 result of flank subsidence. This style of deformation would not produce a true caldera (i.e.
377 cauldron-shaped) unless a summit loading effect is added to the overall process.

378 Finally, the initial slope of the cone also plays an important role in the shape of the
379 caldera in the flank subsidence process. With slopes more than 15 degrees, the summit
380 loading effect allows the formation of a perfectly circular caldera similar to that described
381 above in the summit loading section (Fig. 8a). The normal fault is an additional factor
382 speeding up the process, facilitating a greater amount of subsidence along the ring fault and
383 lowering part of the caldera. With slopes less than 15 degrees, the driving factor is mainly
384 flank subsidence, with the caldera breached and open on the footwall (Fig. 8b). This reveals
385 that one process may be balanced by another, which results in a different final configuration
386 (i.e. circular or breached calderas).

387

388 *Flank sliding* (Fig. 3d)

389 Another way to reduce lateral confinement is flank sliding, which is probably the most
390 widespread instability encountered on volcanoes. It generally leaves a well-identified
391 horseshoe scar. Numerous models have been proposed to explain these instabilities, including
392 dyke or magma emplacement (e.g. Voight et al. 1981; Dieterich 1988 ; McGuire et al. 1990;
393 Delanay et al. 1998 ; Tibaldi 2001), earthquakes (Ando 1979; Montaldo et al. 1996), a weak
394 decollement horizon within the edifice (e.g. van Wyk de Vries et al. 2000, Merle and Lénat
395 2003; Oehler et al. 2005), excess pore pressures due to intrusion (e.g. Voight and Elsworth
396 1997; Elsworth and Day 1999), regional faulting (e.g. Hall et al. 1999; Ventura et al. 1999;
397 Merle et al. 2001), cryptodome emplacement (e.g. Donnadieu et al. 2001), volcano spreading

398 (van Wyk de Vries and Francis 1997), changing sea levels (Firth et al. 1996) and
399 hydrothermal alteration (e.g. Lopez and Williams 1993; van Wyk de Vries et al. 2000; Reid et
400 al. 2001). It has also been proposed that caldera formation may trigger flank sliding (Marti et
401 al. 1997; Hürlihan et al. 2000). As already suggested, several factors may act simultaneously
402 to trigger sliding, and hybrid mechanisms may be common. Whatever the model, flank failure
403 is a common feature on volcanoes, even for low-slope edifices (less than 10 degrees) as
404 shown by the gigantic landslides observed offshore around Hawaii (Moore, 1964) and
405 Reunion Island (Oehler et al. 2007).

406 The sliding scar is a broad depression on the flank of the volcano. It is limited laterally
407 by two fault scarps that are generally divergent from top to bottom along the flank (i.e.
408 horseshoe shape), but which can also be perfectly parallel (but not perfectly straight) as
409 observed on Piton de la Fournaise, which is a striking example of a hydrothermal caldera
410 generated from flank sliding (Merle and Lénat 2003).

411 In experiments where sliding results from a decollement horizon located within the
412 flank of the edifice, for example an altered layer, the timing of events is always the same. The
413 sliding starts downslope at the base of the edifice by a succession of arcuate normal faults,
414 which develop successively backward and upslope. Laterally, these normal faults rotate into
415 the direction of the slide and progressively form the two boundaries of the channel. On top of
416 the edifice, caldera initiation does not start unless the lateral confining stress is adequately
417 reduced, which is achieved only if the head of the slide reaches sufficiently close to the weak
418 core. Caldera formation is then very similar to that described previously and is related to the
419 spreading of the weak core towards the free boundary.

420 In experiments, flank sliding is not an instantaneous process, but results from the slow
421 deformation of a decollement horizon. In this case, the timescale of both sliding and caldera
422 formation is similar (see “rate of caldera formation” section). The question may be asked as

423 whether rapid sliding over the space of minutes as frequently observed on volcanoes can
424 generate hydrothermal calderas. Although we have not conducted experiments of this type,
425 experiments with a high-velocity rate normal fault (see the previous “flank subsidence”
426 section) suggest that gravity instabilities still prevail along the sliding scar, preventing the
427 formation of hydrothermal calderas. In a way similar to regional faulting experiments, faults
428 are expected to develop successively backward at a rapid time interval (i.e. at least a hundred
429 years). These faults would regularly crosscut the weak core, disrupting its slow spreading to
430 the lateral free boundary.

431 It is likely that the presence of a steeply sloped summit may trigger caldera initiation
432 before confinement is reduced enough by lateral sliding. In this case, an incipient but circular
433 caldera may form first and then partly collapse in the slide, in turn enhancing the caldera
434 collapse along the ring fault.

435

436 **Natural cases**

437 *Summit loading* (Fig. 9a). Aoba Island, Vanuatu, is an elongated edifice, with two well
438 developed rifts and a broad summit plateau that hosts a caldera lake with strong thermal
439 activity and frequent phreatic eruptions (Warden 1970). We have generated a digital elevation
440 model from bathymetry and topographic maps, which is shown in Figure 9. There is a 2 km
441 wide caldera with an acid lake, enclosed within a larger 4.5 km wide caldera. The surrounding
442 plateau is 8 km wide, much larger than the caldera. The inner caldera has a clear rim of
443 eruption products and is clearly a product of phreatomagmatic explosive activity. However,
444 the outer plateau has no clear eruptive products associated with it, and has a form more akin
445 to the summit flattening observed in the experiments. In addition, the northeast and southwest
446 flanks, at right angles to the rifts, are convex-sloped with steep portions. These flanks could
447 be the equivalent to the slightly steepened zones in summit flattening experiments.

448 Aoba has the morphology expected for a summit loading case; the summit is flattened
449 over a significantly larger area than the eruptive caldera, and slight flank steepening is
450 observed. While large flat areas could be created by the infilling of a previously-formed
451 caldera, such a scenario cannot explain the wide plateau area outside the caldera structure.
452 This outer plateau is more akin to the summit flattening observed in the experiments. Also,
453 there are clear signs of a strong hydrothermal system active within the cone, a feature
454 expected to accompany the summit flattening process.

455 If the deformation is still active, the continued spreading of the flanks may generate a
456 more pronounced caldera and a flank failure. As slopes are steepest to the north on Aoba, it is
457 this direction that is most likely to fail. If failure is a progressive spreading event, then a
458 possible reorientation of the rift zone around the mobile sector may occur, leading to an
459 arcuate rift zone.

460

461 *Flank spreading* (Fig. 9b). Casita Volcano, Nicaragua is the type case of flank spreading (van
462 Wyk de Vries et al. 2000). The volcano has been inactive for several thousand years but has a
463 very strongly developed hydrothermal system. The summit area is flattened, while the mid
464 flanks are significantly bulged to create the convex - concave – convex shape (Cecchi et al.
465 2005). One side, facing south, has also slid on a basal ductile pumice layer, to create the flank
466 slide that produced the 1998 landslide (Kerle et al 2001). The old pit crater that forms the
467 continuation of the summit in Figure 9b is probably an explosive or magmatic related pit
468 structure.

469 The upper area of Casita has not yet formed a clear caldera structure, as the rate and
470 time of deformation are not yet sufficient. Yet the headscar structure is already well
471 preserved. In the eroded valleys on the Casita structure, hydrothermally altered rock and
472 breccia are exposed. In addition there are active fumaroles, and these features indicate the

473 proximity of the altered zone to the surface. If the deformation at Casita is still active, which
474 is likely as fumaroles indicate an active hydrothermal system, and fault structures are very
475 fresh, then a progressively more pronounced upper caldera-like structure will be formed. At
476 the same time, the sliding sector may eventually accelerate to form a sector collapse (van
477 Wyk de Vries et al. 2000).

478

479 *Flank subsidence* (Fig. 9c). Nuku Hiva Island is the largest shield volcano in the Marquesas
480 Archipelago (French Polynesia) and displays two hemispheric nested calderas overhanging
481 the sea. Geological data do not support the occurrence of large individual eruptions to empty a
482 reservoir large enough to explain the collapse of such giant calderas, over 16 km wide for the
483 largest (Maury et al. 2005). The rough shape of the island is that of an ellipse cut southward
484 by a straight line oriented N75E, which is part of a regional vertical fault visible on the
485 bathymetry. This indicates that the southern half of the initial island has subsided (Merle et al.
486 2006). The interpretation of these available geological data leads to the conclusion that the
487 regional fault N75E which cuts the island in the middle, not far from the main eruptive vents,
488 is an efficient way to provide a free boundary along which lateral flow of the hydrothermal
489 system may occur. This flow may trigger the collapse of the two calderas in the still emerged
490 part of the island. The formation of two nested calderas may result from the initiation of a
491 fracture on the floor of the flat depression, which once it becomes laterally connected to the
492 former ring fault, is likely to initiate a split of the flat depression into two individual areas that
493 then evolve separately. Such an evolution can be observed in some experiments (see Fig. 7 in
494 Merle et al. 2006). Other islands in the Marquesas, like Ua Huka and Hiva Oa, reveal
495 identical features suggesting a common evolution: hydrothermal calderas resulting from
496 regional faulting (Merle et al. 2006).

497

498 *Flank sliding* (Fig 9d). Piton de la Fournaise volcano (Reunion Island) exhibits an unusual
499 structure in that caldera and landslide structures appear to be blended. The scar of the Grand
500 Brûlé flank landslide merges with the Enclos Caldera. We have shown above that the standard
501 model for the Enclos caldera formation is quite unlikely, suggesting that hydrothermal
502 alteration may have generated it. The landslide origin for the Grand Brûlé is well established,
503 the principal evidence being (i) the depression bounded by the subvertical walls to the north
504 and the south and (ii) the products found on the submarine part of the flank (Labazuy 1996).
505 The base of the landslide is known from drilling and is located at a depth of 1000 m, which is
506 the top of a large intrusive cumulate complex 5-6 km thick corresponding to a large volcanic
507 center predating Piton de la Fournaise. The complex is overlain by landslide-derived material
508 indicating that a mechanical discontinuity coincides with the top of the hypovolcanic
509 complex. The width of the scar at the surface virtually matches that of the underlying
510 intrusive complex as inferred from gravity studies (Malengreau et al. 1999; Lénat et al. 2001).
511 Thus, a shallow, low-angle sliding plane, located at the top of the intrusive center, is likely to
512 initiate a slow landslide that has removed a sufficient proportion of the flank to trigger flow-
513 like behaviour of the hydrothermally altered zone to generate the Enclos caldera (compare Fig
514 3d and Fig. 9d).

515

516

517 **Caldera shape**

518

519 In a way similar to magmatic calderas, the shape of hydrothermal calderas is roughly
520 circular. This is not surprising, as the heat source (i.e., the magma chamber or the dyke/sill
521 complex) is generally considered as an ovoid arranged around the central magma feeding
522 system and generally circular in horizontal cross-section. Heat radiates from this central

523 source; as a result, the hydrothermal system must also display a roughly upper hemispherical
524 shape. In plan view, it is thus inferred that the hydrothermal system corresponds to a halo
525 around the magma chamber. As a natural example, such a shape is clearly observed at Piton
526 de la Fournaise from geoelectrical studies (Lénat et al. 2000).

527 It follows that the shape of the caldera strictly matches the shape of the weak core
528 underneath. Changing the shape of the ductile body in experiments always changes the shape
529 of the caldera accordingly (Merle and Lénat 2003; Merle et al. 2006 ; Barde-Cabusson, 2007;
530 Barde-Cabusson and Merle 2007). Thus both size and shape of hydrothermal calderas is
531 dependant on the extent of the clay-rich core underneath.

532 The large size of some hydrothermal calderas, however, also raises the issue of the
533 relationship between the heat source and the hydrothermal system. In other words, there is an
534 apparent mismatch to solve between the existence of a small magma chamber and a large
535 hydrothermal system. At Piton de la Fournaise, the April 2007 eruption and the spectacular
536 collapse of the Dolomieu crater clearly revealed that the withdrawal of a simple single
537 chamber resulted in the collapse of its roof. However, the magmatic system is certainly more
538 complex than a single chamber, consisting of multiple storage reservoirs and surrounding
539 intrusions including a well-developed plexus of dykes and sills. Dykes in particular are
540 arranged radially around the magma chamber or along the rift zones, constituting both an
541 efficient way to transport heat away from the center of the edifice and a multiple drainage
542 system along which hot water may enhance rock alteration. Dyke length frequently reaches
543 several kilometres, with terminations far distant from the shallow magma central reservoir.
544 We propose that this is the complete magmatic system, not only the shallow reservoir, which
545 generates an extensive hydrothermal system. Support for this idea may be found at Piton de la
546 Fournaise; the Enclos caldera displays two lateral extensions (i.e. two lobes on map view)
547 along the two rift zones, suggesting that these rift zones may have played the role of two

548 drains facilitating hot fluid circulation and thus further hydrothermal alteration along their
549 axes.

550

551

552 **Rate of caldera formation**

553

554 Time is needed to achieve conditions suitable for the initiation of a hydrothermal
555 caldera. It depends on several factors including the climate, the size of the volcano and the
556 nature of the hostrock. A wet climate is believed to favour alteration, especially if the upper
557 part of the edifice comprises highly permeable rocks. At Piton de la Fournaise, which is an
558 oceanic island in the South Tropical Zone (Indian Ocean), it may rain up to 12 meters a year
559 in the Enclos Caldera. Surface runoff is very limited, as water penetrates rapidly down in the
560 highly permeable rocks of the caldera floor.

561 The geological history of Piton de La Fournaise allows an estimate of the time needed
562 to develop a deeply altered core large enough to trigger the deformation. The 4500 year old
563 Enclos Caldera is surrounded by three larger and older calderas, which formed at about
564 65 000, 150 000 and 290 000 years (Bachèlery et Mairine 1990; Gillot et al. 1990). The gap
565 between successive collapses appears to be progressively shorter and correlated to the size
566 reduction of each caldera. As a rough approximation deduced from the ages of the successive
567 calderas, the time needed to alter an edifice is several tens of thousands of years for a 10 km-
568 wide caldera and on the order of a hundred thousand years for a 15-30 km-wide caldera.
569 Smaller calderas may develop more rapidly; the Casita structures in Nicaragua may have
570 formed during 8,000 years of alteration (van Wyk de Vries et al. 2000). At the very smallest
571 and most rapid scale, the small (200 m wide) scar structure at Momotombo, Nicaragua, has

572 formed through intense high temperature alteration and flank spreading in less than 100 years
573 (Cecchi et al. 2005).

574 It is more difficult to assess the time needed for caldera formation when ductile
575 deformation starts. This process can be related to several factors such as summit loading and
576 flank sliding, the degree of alteration, or the mineralogical composition of the weak core,
577 especially the amount of clay minerals. Despite these uncertainties, creep-like movement of
578 clay is considered to range from a few millimetres to a few centimetres per year to allow slow
579 and progressive collapse during caldera formation. However, this also means that the overall
580 process would be completed within several hundred years, or a thousand years for very large
581 calderas.

582 One may argue that the long timescales of hydrothermal calderas indicate that this
583 mechanism is actually insignificant, masked by other mechanisms which are more numerous
584 and take place on much faster timescales. Piton de la Fournaise volcano shows clearly that
585 while small-scale drainage calderas (i.e. magmatic calderas) can occur many times as revealed
586 by repeated collapses of the Dolomieu crater, the large hydrothermal caldera could still form
587 independently.

588

589 **Discussion**

590

591 Three models of caldera formation may be identified. The standard magmatic caldera
592 is related to the emptying of a magma chamber during eruption or lateral withdrawal. The
593 second type of caldera results from the sinking of either a dense intrusive complex or deep
594 olivine cumulates (Walker 1984). The third model shown in this paper involves rock
595 alteration around magma chambers and intrusive bodies, forming what we call a hydrothermal
596 caldera. There is similarity between the second and the third models, because both types result

597 from the slow deformation of a ductile core within the volcano as opposed to magmatic
598 calderas which are based on magma withdrawal. The dense intrusive body sinks whereas
599 hydrothermally altered rocks spread and/or rise. Clearly, these two processes can operate at
600 the same time on similar geological timescales and be complementary.

601 Regarding caldera formation, what is conceptually required is a magma reservoir, a
602 deep intrusive body and a large aureole of hydrothermally altered rocks (Fig. 10). Each of the
603 three elements may generate a caldera. As mentioned above, interactions among the three
604 types of caldera may be envisaged. For example, hydrothermally altered rocks surrounding a
605 magma chamber may flow or collapse in into the chamber, following partial magma
606 withdrawal, which may form a hybrid magma-hydrothermal caldera. Another example is a
607 hydrothermal caldera that destabilises a magma chamber, provoking eruptions. However,
608 different types of calderas may be juxtaposed in the field without any interaction. This is the
609 case at Piton de La Fournaise where the small magmatic caldera (the Dolomieu crater) on top
610 of the cone is located within the large hydrothermal “Enclos Fouqué” caldera.

611 It is interesting to consider what sort of phenomena may accompany a hydrothermal
612 collapse. The progressive sinking of the summit will be accompanied by the opening of
613 fractures, seismic activity and disturbance of the hydrothermal and magmatic systems.
614 Phreatic and phreatomagmatic eruptions could be common. These may be produced from the
615 opening fractures, as the summit area may be constricted by the flexural deformation. If the
616 flanks of the volcano are deformed outwards, flank sliding may occur which may guide the
617 hydrothermal collapse in one direction, creating a feedback between the hydrothermal
618 collapse and flank sector sliding.

619 Other volcanoes, such as Poas in Costa Rica (Borgia et al. 1990) and Aoba in Vanuatu,
620 have notably wide flat summit areas, strong hydrothermal systems and calderas that are much
621 smaller than the flat area. The active inner caldera of Aoba is about half the diameter of the

622 outer flat area. These contrasting basaltic and andesitic arc volcanoes may, like Piton de la
623 Fournaise, host hydrothermal calderas. The flat Poas summit area is well formed and may be
624 accompanied by flank spreading that allows the hydrothermal system to spread (Borgia et al.
625 1990), while Aoba (Warden 1970) has what appears to be a ripening summit loading type of
626 caldera.

627 Large silicic systems, such as Yellowstone (USA), involve repeated caldera collapse at
628 a crustal scale and are associated with strong hydrothermal activity. It is clear from the
629 isotopic signature of some magmas that there is strong interaction between hydrothermally
630 altered rock and the magma (Hildreth et al 1991, Bindemn and Valley 2000). It would be
631 therefore interesting to investigate the mechanical role of alteration in such large systems,
632 where deformation can occur over timescales of $\sim 10^5$ years.

633

634

635 **Concluding remarks**

636

637 Hydrothermal caldera formation following ductile deformation of a deeply altered core
638 in a volcanic edifice is a new concept, the principal mechanisms of which are still poorly
639 understood. We believe, however, that it provides a consistent alternative to the standard
640 model in situations comprising a small magma chamber versus a wide caldera. Our new
641 model is especially well adapted to large shield volcanoes that do not store large volumes of
642 magma in the upper edifice, and thus do not have the ability to form a wide caldera collapse
643 in a single event.

644 The different modes and mechanisms proposed here result from several field studies
645 and numerous analogue experiments. They are summarized in Table 1. We are aware that this

646 represents the first principles of concept that requires further investigation, especially with
647 careful field studies of large calderas that do not appear to fit with the standard caldera model.

648 Mode I (Ripening) requires sufficient summit loading to form a true cauldron-shaped
649 caldera. The lack of a steep summit slope or a deeply buried weak core do not allow the
650 formation of a flat floor. In this case, summit sagging takes place along a ring fault if flank
651 spreading can occur. However, a new outer flat area may also develop surrounding the
652 sagging summit, forming a flat caldera with a relict summit in its centre. The Ripening Mode
653 probably leads to small amounts of collapse and limited vertical offsets along the ring fault, as
654 the caldera forms only from the flow and deformation of the weak core inside the volcano. In
655 Mode II (Unbuttressing), the weak core can escape laterally, which results in a greater amount
656 of vertical collapse along the ring fault together with a caldera breached on one side.

657 The flank spreading process may be difficult to separate from the Unbuttressing Mode if
658 the lateral push of the weak core overcomes the resisting flank, breaking apart the bulge. This
659 may be considered as another way to unbuttress the volcano and change from flank spreading
660 to flank sliding. The resulting deformation is a caldera breached at the unconfined boundary.
661 For this reason, the summary shown on Table 1 is believed to represent end-members that are
662 likely to be combined in nature to form hybrid mechanisms.

663 In many experiments, the analogue weak core reaches the surface either along the ring
664 fault or in the unbuttressed flank (see Fig 3a, 3d and Fig. 8a). This always coincides with an
665 acceleration of the process and a notable increase of caldera collapse. In nature, outcrops of
666 hydrothermally altered rocks need to be examined and mapped to identify possible
667 relationships with caldera processes. They should appear in the field as a mix of breccias and
668 clay in variable proportions. When such material is not removed at the surface by erosion,
669 dissolution and eruption, we believe that identifying and mapping these altered zones in
670 volcanoes, especially around well developed ring faults, can be an important step. This should

671 be done together with detailed geophysical studies to obtain the distribution of hydrothermally
672 altered material where hydrothermal calderas are suspected.

673

674 **Appendix**

675 Details about the scaling procedure and the experimental devices for each experiment
676 may be found in published studies or theses (Merle and Lénat 2003; Cecchi 2003; Cecchi et
677 al. 2005; Merle et al. 2006, Barde-Cabusson and Merle 2007; Barde-Cabusson 2007).
678 Following a well-founded procedure established for volcanic terranes (e.g. Tibaldi 1995;
679 Merle and Borgia 1996), similarity conditions are achieved by selecting dimensionless
680 numbers that need to maintain the same value in nature and experiments. According to the
681 Buckingham Π theorem, seven dimensionless numbers are required to verify that experiments
682 are geometrically, kinematically and dynamically well-scaled.

683 From those, it can be shown that volcanic cones may be simulated by a dry
684 sand/plastic mixture, a cohesionless brittle material, which properly reproduces the brittle
685 behaviour of non-altered volcanic rocks. To simulate the weak volcanic core, we used silicone
686 putty, a newtonian material able to flow under its own weight, as is hypothesized for the clay-
687 rich core of the volcano. Depending on the time during which motion occurs, silicone is
688 appropriate to simulate ductile materials having a rather high-viscosity ranging from 10^{10} to
689 10^{18} Pa s. Thus, it may be used to simulate either high-viscosity acid lavas (i.e. 10^{10} - 10^{11} Pa s,
690 see experiments about cryptodome intrusion in Mount St Helens, Donnadiou and Merle 1998)
691 or natural clays, which display viscosities of about 10^{17} - 10^{18} Pa s. This is why using silicone
692 to simulate the clay-rich core of a volcano, as in the experiments under consideration makes
693 them properly scaled. In contrast, low-viscosity lavas (10^2 - 10^3 Pa s) of basaltic shields cannot
694 be simulated by silicone; a better analogue material is golden syrup or various types of oils
695 (Galland et al. 2007, Mathieu et al. 2008).

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698

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702

703 REFERENCES

704 Acocella V, Cifelli F, Funiciello R (2000) Analogue models of collapse calderas and
705 resurgent domes. *J Volcanol Geotherm Res* 104: 81-96

706 Ando M (1979) The Hawaii earthquake of November 29, 1975 : low dip angle faulting due to
707 forceful injection of magma. *J Geophys Res* 84: 7616-7626

708 Bachèlery P (1981) Le Piton de la Fournaise (Ile de la Réunion). Etude volcanologique,
709 structurale et pétrologique. PhD thesis, University of Clermont-Ferrand, Clermont-
710 Ferrand

711 Bachèlery P (2007) Fournaise : l'éruption du siècle. *Eruption* 15: 19-21

712 Bachèlery P Mairine P (1990) Evolution volcano-structurale du Piton de la Fournaise depuis
713 0.53 Ma. In : Lénat J.-F (ed.), *Le volcanisme de la Réunion – Monographie*. Cent Rech
714 Volcanol, Clermont-Ferrand, France: 213-242

715 Barde-Cabusson (2007) Formation de caldera par fluage d'un système hydrothermal
716 volcanique, PhD thesis, University of Clermont-Ferrand

717 Barde-Cabusson S Merle O (2007) From steep-slope volcano to flat caldera floor. *Geophys*
718 *Res Lett* 34: L10305, doi: 10.1029/2007GL029784

719 Bindemann I, Valley JW (2000) Formation of low- $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ rhyolites after caldera collapse at
720 Yellowstone, Wyoming, USA. *Geology* 28(8):719-722

721 Borgia A (1994) Dynamic basis for volcanic spreading. *J Geophys Res* 99(17): 17791- 17804

722 Borgia A Burr J Montero W Morales LD Alavarado GE (1990) Fault propagation folds
723 induced by gravitational failure and slumping of the Central Costa Rica Volcanic
724 Range : Implications for large terrestrial and martian volcanic edifices. *J Geophys Res*
725 95: 14357-14382

726 Branney MJ Kokelaar P (1994) Volcanotectonic faulting, soft state deformation, and
727 rheomorphism of tuffs during development of a piecemeal caldera, English Lake
728 District. *Geol Soc Am Bull* 106: 507-530

729 Briole P Bachelery P McGuire B Moss J Ruegg JC Sabourault P (1998) Deformation of Piton
730 de la Fournaise: Evolution of the monitoring techniques and knowledge acquired in the
731 last five years, in *Proceedings, 2nd Workshop on European Laboratory Volcanoes,*
732 *Santorini, Greece, 1996*, edited by R. Casale et al., European Commission, Brussels:
733 467–474

734 Calvari S Spampinato L Lodato L (2006) The 5 avril 2003 vulcanian paroxysmal explosion at
735 Stromboli volcano from field observations and thermal data. *J Volcanol Geotherm Res*
736 149: 160-175

737 Carrasco-Nunez G Vallance JW Rose, WI (1993) A voluminous avalanche-induced lahar
738 from Citlaltepelt volcano, Mexico : implications for hazard assessment. *J Volcanol*
739 *Geotherm Res* 59: 35-46

740 Cecchi E (2003) Reconstruction 3D pour la volcanologie : apports d'une méthode multi-vues
741 par photogrammétrie numérique. PhD Thesis, University of Clermont-Ferrand

742 Cecchi E van Wyk de Vries B Lavest JM (2005) Flank spreading and collapse of weak-cored
743 volcanoes. *Bull Volcanol* 67: 72-91

744 Delaney PT Denlinger RP Lisowsky M Miklius A Okubo PG Okamura AT and Sako MK
745 1998, Volcanic spreading at Kilauea, 1976-1996. *J Geophys Res* 103: 18003-18023

746 Donnadieu F Merle O Besson JL (2001) Volcanic edifice stability during cryptodome
747 intrusion. *Bull Volcanol* 63: 61-72

748 Donnadieu F Merle O. (1998) Experiments on the indentation process during cryptodome
749 intrusion: new insights into Mt St Helens deformation. *Geology* 26: 79-82.

750 Day SJ (1996), Hydrothermal pore fluid pressure and the stability of porous, permeable
751 volcano, *Volcano Instability on the Earth and Other Planets*. Edited by W. J. McGuire,
752 A. P. Jones, and J. Neuberg, *Geol Soc Lond Spec Pub* 110: 77-93.

753 Dieterich JH (1988) Growth and persistence of Hawaiian volcanic rift zones. *J Geophys Res*
754 12: 147–160

755 Druitt TH Sparks RS (1984) On the formation of calderas during ignimbrite eruptions. *Nature*
756 310: 679-681

757 Elsworth D Day S (1999) Flank collapse triggered by intrusion : the Canarian and Cape Verde
758 Archipelagoes. *J Volcanol Geotherm Res* 94: 323-340

759 Finizola A Lénat J-F Macedo O Ramos D Thouret J-C Sortino F (2004) Fluid circulation and
760 structural discontinuities inside Misti volcano (Peru) inferred from self-potential
761 measurements. *J Volcanol Geotherm Res* 135: 343-360.

762 Finizola A Sortino F Lénat J-F Valenza M (2002) Fluid circulation at Stromboli volcano
763 (Aeolian Islands, Italy) from self potential and CO₂ surveys. *J Volcanol Geotherm Res*
764 116: 1-18

765 Finizola A Revil A Rizzo E Piscitelli S Ricci T Morin J Angeletti B Mocochain L Sortino F
766 (2006) Hydrogeological insights at Stromboli volcano (Italy) from geoelectrical,
767 temperature, and CO₂ soil degassing investigations. *Geophys Res Lett* 33: L7304, doi:
768 10.1029/2006GL026842

769 Firth C Stewart L McGuire WJ Kershaw S Vita-Finzi C (1996) Coastal elevation changes in
770 eastern Sicily : Implications for volcano instability at Mount Etna, in McGuire WJ et al.

771 eds, Volcano instability on the Earth and other planets : Geol Soc Lond Spec Publ 110:
772 153-167

773 Frank D (1995) Surficial extent and conceptual model of hydrothermal system at Mount
774 Rainier. *J Volcanol Geotherm Res* 65: 51-80

775 Galland O Cobbold PR Hallot E de Bremond d'Ars J Delavaud G (2006) Use of vegetable oil
776 and silica powder for scale modelling of magmatic intrusion in a deforming brittle crust.
777 *Earth Planet. Sci. Lett.* 243: 786-804.

778 Gillott JE (1987) Clay in engineering geology. *Developments in geotechnical engineering*,
779 Elsevier Science Publishers B. V.

780 Gillot PY Nativel PE Condomines M (1990) Géochronologie du Piton de la Fournaise. In :
781 Lénat J.-F (ed.), *Le volcanisme de la Réunion – Monographie*. Cent Rech Volcanol
782 Clermont-Ferrand, France, 243-256

783 Glicken H Voight B Janda RJ (1981) Rockslide-debris avalanche of May 18, 1980, Mount St.
784 Helens volcano, IAVCEI Symposium on Arc Volcanism, Tokyo and Hakone, 109-110

785 Hall ML Robin C Beate B Mothes P Monzier M (1999) Tungurahua volcano, Ecuador:
786 Structure, eruptive history and hazards. *J Volcanol Geotherm Res* 91: 1-21

787 Hildreth W, Halliday AN, Christensen RL (1991) Isotopic and Chemical Evidence
788 Concerning the Genesis and Contamination of Basaltic and Rhyolitic Magma Beneath
789 the Yellowstone Plateau Volcanic Field, *J Pet* 32: 63-138

790 Hochstein M.P., Browne P.R.L. (2000) Surface manifestations of geothermal systems with
791 volcanic heat sources. In: Sigurdsson, H. (Ed.), *Encyclopedia of Volcanoes*. Academic
792 Press, San Francisco, 835-855

793 Holcomb RT Moore JG Lipman PW Belderson RH (1988) Voluminous submarine lava flows
794 from Hawaiian volcanoes. *Geology* 16: 400-404

795 Hürlimann MN Marti J Ledesma A (2000) Mechanical relationship between catastrophic
796 volcanic landslides and caldera collapses. *Geophys Res Lett* 27: 2393-2396

797 Iverson RM Reid ME LaHusen RG (1997) Debris-flow mobilization from landslides. *Ann*
798 *Rev Earth Planet Sci* 25: 85-138

799 Jackson MPA Vendeville BC. Schultz-Ela D (1994) Structural dynamics of salt systems. *Ann*
800 *Rev Earth Planet Sci* 22: 93-117.

801 Kerle N van Wyk de Vries B (2001) The 1998 debris avalanche at Casita volcano, Nicaragua
802 – Investigation of structural deformation as the cause of slope instability using remote
803 sensing. *J Volcanol Geotherm Res* 105: 49-63.

804
805 Kerr P.F. (1955) Hydrothermal alteration and weathering. In: A. Poldervaart (ed.), *The crust*
806 *of the Earth*. *Geol Soc Am Spec Papers* 62: 525–543

807 Komuro H (1987) Experiments on cauldron formation: a polygonal cauldron and ring
808 fractures. *J Volcanol Geotherm Res* 31: 139-149

809 Labazuy P (1996) Recurrent landslides events on the submarine flank of Piton de la Fournaise
810 volcano (Réunion Island), in McGuire WJ et al. (eds), *Volcano instability on the Earth*
811 *and other planets* : *Geol Soc Lond Spec Publ* 110: 293-305

812 Lénat J.F Robineau B Durand S Bachèlery P (1998) Etude de la zone sommitale du volcan
813 Karthala (Grande Comore) par polarisation spontanée. *C R Acad Sci* 327: 781–788

814 Lenat J.-F Fitterman D. Jackson DB Labazuy P (2000) Geoelectrical structure of the central
815 zone of Piton de la Fournaise volcano (Réunion). *Bull Volcanol* 62: 75-89

816 Lenat J-F Malengreau B Galdéano A (2001) A new model for the evolution of the volcanic
817 island of reunion (Indian Ocean) *J Geophys Res* 106: 8645-8663

818 Lipman PW (1984) The roots of ash flow calderas in western North America: windows into
819 the tops of granitic batholiths. *J Geophys Res* 89: 8801–8841

820 Lipman PW (1997) Subsidence of ash-flow calderas: relation to caldera size and magma
821 chamber geometry. *Bull Volcanol* 59: 198-218

822 Lipman PW (2000b) The central San Juan caldera cluster: regional volcanic framework. Spec
823 Pap Geol Soc Am 346: 9-71

824 Lipman PW (2000a) Calderas. In: Sigurdsson, H. (Ed.), Encyclopedia of Volcanoes.
825 Academic Press, San Francisco, 643-662

826 López DL Williams SN (1993), Catastrophic volcanic collapse: relation to hydrothermal
827 processes, Science 260: 1794-1796.

828 McGuire WJ Pullen AD Saunders SJ (1990) Recent dyke-induced large-scale block
829 movement at Mount Etna and potential slope failure. Nature 343: 357-359

830 Malengreau B Lénat JF Froger JL (1999) Structure of Réunion Island (Indian Ocean) inferred
831 from the interpretation of gravity anomalies. J Volcanol Geotherm Res 88: 131-146

832 Marti J Hurlimann M Ablay GJ Gudmundsson A (1997) Vertical and lateral collapse on
833 Tenerife (Canary islands) and other volcanic ocean islands. Geology 25: 879-882

834 Marti J Ablay GJ Redshaw LT Sparks R.S.J. (1994) Experimental studies of caldera collapse.
835 J Geol Soc (Lond) 151: 919-929

836 Mathieu L van Wyk de Vries B Holohan E Troll V (2008) Dykes, cups, saucers and sills:
837 analogue experiments on magma intrusion into brittle rocks. Earth Planet Sci Let 271: 1-
838 13

839 Maury RC Guille G Legendre C Savanier D Guillou H Rossi P Blais S (2005) Notice
840 explicative, carte géologique de la France (1/50 000), feuille de Nuku Hiva, Polynésie
841 française : Orléans, BRGM, Archipel des marquises : Service Géologique National,
842 Editions du BRGM.

843 Merle O Borgia A (1996), Scaled experiments on volcanic spreading, J Geophys Res 101:
844 13805-13817.

845 Merle O Vidal N van Wyk de Vries B (2001) Experiments on vertical basement fault
846 reactivations below volcanoes. J Geophys Res 106: 2153-2162

847 Merle O Lénat JF (2003) Hybrid collapse mechanism at Piton de la Fournaise volcano,
848 Reunion Island, Indian Ocean. *J Geophys Res* 108: 2166

849 Merle O Barde Cabusson S Maury R Legendre C Guille G Blais S (2006) Volcano core
850 collapse triggered by regional faulting. *J Volcanol Geotherm Res* 158: 269-280

851 Michel S Zlotnicki J (1998) Self-potential and magnetic surveying of La Fournaise Volcano
852 (Reunion Island): Correlations with faulting, fluid circulation, and eruption. *J Geophys*
853 *Res* 103: 17,845–17,857

854 Michon L and Saint-Ange F (2008) The morphology of Piton de la Fournaise basaltic shield
855 volcano (La Reunion Island): characterisation and implication in the volcano evolution.
856 *J Geophys Res* 113: doi:10.29/2005JB004118

857 Middleton GV Wilcock PR (1996) *Mechanics in the Earth and Environmental Sciences*.
858 Cambridge Univ. Press, New York.

859 Mohamed-Abchir MA Semet MP Boudon G Ildefonse P Bachèlery P Clochiatti R (1998)
860 Huge hydrothermal explosive activity on Piton de la Fournaise, Reunion Island: The
861 Bellecombe ash member, 2700 BC, in proceedings, 2nd workshop on European laboratory
862 volcanoes, Santorini, Greece, edited by R Casale et al.: 447-455

863 Montaldo A Vicinguerra S Menza S Patane G (1996) Recent seismicity of Mount Etna :
864 Implications for flank instability, in McGuire WJ et al. (eds), *Volcano instability on the*
865 *Earth and other planets* : *Geol Soc Lond Spec Publ* 110: 169-177

866 Moore JG (1964) Giant submarine landslides on the Hawaiian Ridge. U.S. Geological Survey
867 Professional paper 501: 95-98

868 Munro DC Rowland SK (1996), Caldera morphology in the western Galápagos and
869 implications for volcano eruptive behaviour and mechanisms of caldera formation. *J*
870 *Volcanol Geotherm Res* 72: 85-100

871 Nercessian A Hirn A Lepine JC Sapin M (1996) Internal structure of Piton de la Fournaise
872 Volcano from seismic wave propagation and earthquake distribution. *J Volcanol*
873 *Geotherm Res* 70: 123-143

874 Oehler JF van Wyk de Vries B Labazuy P (2005) Landslides and spreading of oceanic hot-
875 spot and arc shield volcanoes on Low Strength Layers (LSLs): an analogue modelling
876 approach. *J Volcanol Geotherm Res* 144: 169-189

877 Oehler JF Lénat JF Labazuy Ph (2007) Growth and collapse of the Reunion Island volcanoes.
878 *Bull Volcanol* DOI 10.1007/s00445-007-0163-0

879 Oftedahl C Cauldrons of the Permian Oslo rift, *J. Volcanol. Geotherm. Res.*, 3, 343-371, 1978

880 Reid ME Sisson TW Brien DL (2001) Volcano collapse promoted by hydrothermal alteration
881 and edifice shape, Mount Rainier, Washington. *Geology* 29: 779-782

882 Roche O Druitt TH Merle O (2000), Experimental study of caldera formation. *J Geophys Res*
883 105: 395-416.

884 Rousset D Lesquer A Bonneville A Lénat JF (1989) Complete gravity study of Piton de la
885 Fournaise volcano, Reunion. *J Volcanol Geotherm Res* 36: 37-52

886 Siebert L (1984) Large volcanic debris avalanches : characteristics of source areas, deposits
887 and associated eruptions. *J Volcanol Geotherm Res* 22: 163-197

888 Smith RL Bailey RA (1968) Resurgent cauldrons. *Mem Geol Soc Am* 116: 613-662

889 Tibaldi A (1995) Morphology of pyroclastic cones and tectonics. *J Geophys Res* 100: 24521-
890 24535.

891 Tibaldi A (2001) Multiple sector collapses at Stromboli volcano, Italy : how they work. *Bull*
892 *Volcanol* 63: 112-125

893 Tort A Finizola A The buried caldera of Misti volcano, Peru, revealed by combining a self-
894 potential survey with elliptic Fourier function analysis of topography. *J Volcanol*
895 *Geotherm Res* 141: 283-297

896 Troll VR Walter TR Schmincke HU (2002) Cyclic caldera collapse: piston or piecemeal
897 subsidence? Field and experimental evidence. *Geology* 30: 135-138

898 Van Wyk de Vries B Francis P (1997) Catastrophic collapse at stratovolcanoes induced by
899 gradual volcano spreading. *Nature* 387: 387–390

900 van Wyk de Vries B Kerle N Petley D (2000) Sector collapse forming at Casita volcano,
901 Nicaragua. *Geology* 28:167-170.

902 Ventura G Vilardo G Bruno PP (1999) The role of flank failure in modifying the shallow
903 plumbing system of volcanoes : an example from Somma-Vesuvius, Italy. *Geophys Res*
904 *Lett* 26: 3681-3684

905 Voight B Glicken H Janda J Douglas PM (1981) Catastrophic rockslide avalanche of may 18,
906 in the 1980 Eruptions of Mount St Helens, Washington, P.W. Lipman and D.R.
907 Mullineaux (eds), *U S Geol Surv Prof Pap* 125: 347-377

908 Voight B Elsworth D (1997) Failure of volcano slope. *Géotechnique* 47: 1-31

909 Walker GPL (1960a) The amygdale minerals in the Tertiary lavas of Ireland. III. Regional
910 distribution. *Mineral Mag* 32: 503–527

911 Walker GPL (1960b) Zeolite zones and dyke distribution in relation to the structure of the
912 basalts of eastern Ireland. *J Geol* 68: 515–528

913 Walker GPL (1984) Downsag calderas, ring faults, caldera sizes, and incremental caldera
914 growth. *J Geophys Res B*: 8,407–8,416

915 Walker GPL (1988) Three Hawaiian calderas: an origin through loading by shallow
916 intrusions. *J Geophys Res* 93: 14773-14784

917 Warden AJ (1970) Evolution of Aoba caldera volcano, New Hebrides. *Bull Volcanol* 34: 107-
918 140

919 Yokoyama I A (1981) geophysical interpretation of the 1883 Krakatau eruption, *J Volcanol*
920 *Geotherm Res* 9: 359-378

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924 **Figure captions**

925

926 Figure 1. Shape of the hydrothermal weak core below the Enclos Caldera of Piton de la
927 Fournaise volcano (Reunion Island, Indian Ocean) as deduced from geoelectric studies (after
928 Lénat et al. 2000). The weak core appears as a low-angle cone centred below the Dolomieu
929 crater and stretched to the caldera boundary. Its lower extension is not known. At bottom,
930 three photos display a panoramic view of the caldera rim on the sides and the central cone.

931

932 Figure 2. The two principal modes, Ripening (I) and Unbuttressing (II), for hydrothermal
933 caldera formation (see text for explanation).

934

935 Figure 3. Experiments on hydrothermal calderas showing the different types of deformation
936 possible during collapse of a hydrothermal system. a) Summit loading (Barde-Cabusson and
937 Merle 2007) b) Flank spreading (Cecchi et al. 2005) c) Flank subsidence (Merle et al. 2006)
938 and d) Flank sliding (Merle and Lénat 2003).

939

940 Figure 4. Summit loading model. The slow ductile deformation of the weak core leads
941 successively to the formation of an upper flat-lying area (4b), the formation of a ring fault
942 (4c) and the caldera collapse (4d)

943

944 Figure 5. Flank spreading model. The deformation of the weak core leads to summit sagging
945 in the centre of a flat-lying area collapsing along a ring fault. On the flanks, a bulge limited at
946 its base by a thrust fault develops as a result of lateral spreading of the weak core.

947

948 Figure 6. Unbuttressing mode. An unconfined boundary (resulting here from flank sliding)
949 makes possible slow lateral spreading of the weak core and the formation of an upper caldera.
950

951 Figure 7. Cross-section within the footwall of a regional normal fault in a flank subsidence
952 experiment. The ridge in front of the footwall is similar to the bulge/thrust association
953 observed in the flank spreading model and results from lateral flow of the weak core.
954

955 Figure 8. Two experiments of flank subsidence achieved by normal faulting in the underlying
956 basement. Initial slopes steeper than 15 degrees initiate a dominating summit loading process
957 (a) whereas initial slopes less than 15 degrees initiate an unbuttressing process (b). The
958 unbuttressing process leads to a caldera breached on the footwall.
959

960 Figure 9. Natural examples of hydrothermal calderas. a) Aoba volcano, Vanuatu. b) Casita
961 volcano, Nicaragua. c) Nuku-Hiva volcano, French Polynesia. d) Piton de la Fournaise
962 volcano, La Reunion Island. See text for explanation.
963

964 Figure 10. Schematic representation of the three elements in a volcanic edifice, which may
965 lead to caldera formation. The shallow reservoir generates a magmatic caldera whereas the
966 clay-rich altered core generates a large hydrothermal caldera. The deep intrusive body may
967 also generate a caldera-like structure when sinking into the crust.
968

969 Table 1. Types of hydrothermal calderas as a function of flank spreading, flank subsidence,
970 flank sliding versus summit loading. A dominant summit loading effect leads to cauldron-
971 shaped calderas whereas dominant flank subsidence or flank collapse leads to calderas

972 breached on the unbuttressed boundary. A cone-shaped caldera resembles a pointed hat with
973 flat edges limited by the ring fault.

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